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Sustaining the Nursing Workforce in Times of Crisis: A Case Study

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing global nursing shortage has been acutely exacerbated in Lebanon by the severe economic crisis that began in 2019, leading to an alarming rise in nurse emigration and threatening the sustainability of healthcare delivery. This cross-sectional study evaluates the perceived value of monetary and non-monetary retention measures among nurses employed at a private hospital in Beirut. A structured survey, completed by 54 respondents, assessed ten key factors—including salary, work environment, professional development, and scheduling flexibility—under both normal and crisis conditions using a 5-point Likert scale. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses revealed that while salary remained the most highly valued factor, particularly during crisis, non-monetary measures such as workplace safety and stability were consistently rated as nearly equally significant. These findings underscore the critical need for health administrators and policymakers to adopt a multifaceted retention strategy that extends beyond financial incentives to include improvements in working conditions, especially in contexts of prolonged socio-economic instability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global shortage of nurses presents a pressing challenge to health systems worldwide, particularly as aging populations increase demand for care. While this is a universal concern, its impact is more acute in low- and middle-income countries, where resources are limited and healthcare infrastructures are strained. Lebanon exemplifies this crisis, having experienced chronic under-staffing in the nursing sector even before the onset of a national economic collapse in 2019. The compounded effects of financial instability, sociopolitical unrest, and large-scale emigration have intensified the exodus of qualified nurses, placing the sustainability of hospital-based care at critical risk.

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Since 2019, Lebanon has witnessed a significant deterioration in public services, currency value, and wages, which has severely impacted the healthcare workforce. For nurses, real incomes have drastically declined, eroding their purchasing power and compromising their ability to meet basic needs. Simultaneously, hospitals are constrained by limited budgets and third-party reimbursement systems, making it difficult to offer competitive salaries or benefits. This environment has created a scenario where nurse emigration is not only prevalent but increasingly viewed as a necessity rather than a choice.

Within this complex context, monetary incentives—chiefly salary—are often perceived as the primary driver of job satisfaction and retention. However, emerging research highlights the growing importance of non-monetary factors, particularly in resource-constrained settings. These include a safe and stable work environment, opportunities for professional development, flexible scheduling, and supportive workplace culture. For hospital administrators with limited financial flexibility, identifying and investing in such non-monetary measures could offer a feasible pathway to enhance nurse retention.

This study focuses on understanding how nurses in a private hospital in Beirut evaluate various retention measures under normal circumstances and during economic crisis. Using a structured survey instrument, the research captures nurses' perceptions of ten key factors—one monetary and nine non-monetary—rated on a 5-point Likert scale. By comparing the values assigned to these measures across different economic scenarios, the study aims to identify which incentives are consistently prioritized and whether their relative importance shifts in times of financial hardship.

The insights derived from this study are intended to inform hospital-level and national policies aimed at strengthening the nursing workforce. Given the high risk of attrition and the growing global demand for skilled nurses, retention strategies must be evidence-based and contextually relevant. By highlighting the specific needs and preferences of nurses within Lebanon's ongoing crisis, this research provides actionable recommendations for developing more effective, sustainable, and affordable workforce policies.

2. BACKGROUND

Nurses are the cornerstone of healthcare delivery, translating doctors' directives into concrete patient care, monitoring clinical status, and providing emotional support. They play central roles in managing chronic illnesses and palliative care, and they spearhead public health initiatives such as vaccination and health education campaigns—roles that became especially prominent during the COVID-19 pandemic. Their compassionate care enhances quality, reduces morbidity and mortality, and improves overall patient outcomes. However, the physically and emotionally demanding nature of nursing—exacerbated by burnout—remains a growing concern, particularly amid aging populations that strain healthcare systems globally.

Evidence consistently shows that better nurse-to-patient ratios are associated with lower mortality, fewer complications and infections, enhanced patient satisfaction, shorter hospital stays, and reduced readmissions. These benefits often outweigh the costs of hiring more staff, while also improving nurse well-being and retention. Higher levels of nursing education, notably baccalaureate degrees, are linked to lower surgical mortality and reduced failure-to-rescue rates, leading many countries to mandate minimum proportions of BSN-educated nurses as a quality standard. Clinical judgment, developed through education, training, and mentorship—including at least two years of bedside experience—is critical for early complication detection and proactive care. Unfortunately, the emigration of experienced nurses undermines mentorship for junior staff and diminishes institutional capacity. Moreover, positive care environments where nurses feel valued and supported correlate with lower mortality and failure-to-rescue risks, and satisfied nurses contribute to both better patient care and institutional effectiveness.

A nursing shortage arises when demand surpasses supply, manifesting in staffing gaps, reliance on overtime or temporary staff, and poor outcome indicators. This is a dynamic imbalance that signals potential healthcare system failure rather than a fixed numerical benchmark. Globally, the WHO projects that by 2030 there will be a need for 13 million additional nurses, with global demand for health workers reaching 80 million—about 60% being nurses—while supply may only reach 65 million, leaving a shortfall of 15 million. Lebanon graduates approximately 2,500 nurses annually, with about 47% holding BS degrees and the remainder vocational qualifications. Despite this, nurse density has dropped from 2.72 per 1,000 in 2014 to 1.51 in 2020, far below European and American averages. Between 2009 and 2014, active nurses increased by 35%, but inactive nurses grew by 86%, while overseas-registered nurses surged by 173%, reflecting strong emigration trends and a workforce skewed toward younger ages.

Job satisfaction plays a central role in recruitment and retention. Frameworks like the McCloskey–Mueller Satisfaction Scale highlight eight dimensions spanning both monetary and non-monetary drivers, while Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory differentiates between hygiene factors (salary, safety, policies) and motivators (recognition, advancement). Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs reveals that nurses in crisis contexts often prioritize duty over basic needs—an unsustainable imbalance—while Social Exchange Theory emphasizes the instability that arises when nurses give more than they receive. Monetary incentives can be effective for recruitment, especially in underserved areas, but salary alone is rarely enough for long-term retention. Non-monetary factors such as safety, stability, professional development, continuing education, work-life balance, technology integration, and emotional support are equally critical. In Lebanon, workplace violence, job instability, and limited career progression are key drivers of turnover, while supportive leadership, flexible scheduling, and technology-enhanced work environments can boost satisfaction and retention.

The emigration of nurses from Lebanon further compounds shortages, increasing workloads for those who remain, disrupting patient care quality, and eroding mentorship capacity. Despite steady graduation rates, the pipeline of experienced nurses willing to remain in current conditions is shrinking, exacerbated by global competition for talent. Lebanon’s ongoing economic crisis has slashed nurse salaries from pre-crisis levels of USD 1,000–2,000 to USD 250–700, pushing many to seek opportunities abroad. By 2021, over 3,500 nurses—about 20% of those registered—had submitted travel documents, and more than half of those still working intended to emigrate within two years. Alarming, up to 20% of BSN graduates leave within two years of completing their studies, resulting in a dual loss of both capacity and mentorship.

Applying human resource theories to the emigration challenge highlights several strategies. Social Exchange Theory suggests enhancing the perceived benefits of staying while reducing the costs of migration, while the Theory of Planned Behavior underscores the need to address attitudes, social norms, and perceived control over migration. Common retention strategies include strengthening professional development, broadening recruitment through vocational pathways, reintegrating inactive nurses, and—though controversial—importing foreign nurses. For Lebanon, tailored approaches should focus on non-monetary incentives such as mentorship and safer workplace policies, reactivating eligible nurses through flexible arrangements, engaging the diaspora through tele-mentoring and short-term return programs, advocating for nurse-patient ratio norms and education standards, and leveraging technology to ease workloads and upskill staff. Ethical considerations remain critical, as international recruitment can drain donor countries and systemic undervaluation of the profession must be addressed.

Future research should explore emerging areas like the integration of AI and humanoid robots in healthcare, examining their impact on nurse workload, care quality, satisfaction, and employment dynamics. While technology can streamline nursing tasks, its uneven implementation and unintended consequences must be studied carefully. Research priorities include assessing the effectiveness of digital tools in reducing fatigue and turnover, understanding their role in professional isolation versus

satisfaction, developing strategies for safe integration of robotics without undermining human empathy, and conducting comparative and longitudinal studies on re-entry models and emotional support interventions. Policy-focused research on the efficacy of staffing regulations and education mandates is also essential to building sustainable retention frameworks in both Lebanon and other resource-constrained contexts.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study investigates the relative value nurses assign to various retention measures—both monetary and non-monetary—implemented by a private hospital in the Beirut area. A measure's value is defined by its mean rating on a five-point Likert scale. The ten measures examined include one monetary factor, salary, and nine non-monetary factors: a safe work environment, a stable work environment, opportunities for career advancement and promotion, ongoing education and training, a flexible work schedule allowing work–life balance, a flexible schedule permitting an additional job, the availability of technology and resources, family ties, and workplace socialization. The analysis seeks to determine whether certain measures are consistently valued more highly than others, providing an evidence base for targeted retention and recruitment strategies that can direct limited resources toward the most impactful interventions. This work is situated within the broader challenges facing Lebanon's healthcare system, which has long struggled to retain qualified nurses—an issue that has intensified since the post-2019 economic crisis and the resulting emigration wave. Given the central role of nursing in achieving optimal healthcare delivery, the study's findings aim to inform policies for workforce stabilization.

The study complied with all applicable ethical requirements. Approval was obtained from the hospital's ethics committee prior to commencement, and the principal investigator completed the Protecting Human Research Participants course. Participation in the survey was voluntary, and all responses were anonymous and confidential. Data were collected solely for educational and research purposes. The research adopts a positivist paradigm, assuming that social reality is observable and measurable, aligning with the use of a cross-sectional survey as the primary data collection tool. The survey targeted nurses working in a private, university-affiliated hospital in the Beirut area.

A quantitative approach was employed, with all responses captured on a five-point Likert scale to produce numerical data. Demographic information was also quantified for analysis. Descriptive statistics—means, standard deviations, and distributions—and inferential testing through paired-samples t-tests were used to evaluate differences between conditions. The survey consisted of five parts: demographics; retention measures in normal economic conditions; retention measures in economic crisis conditions; non-monetary measures only in normal conditions; and non-monetary measures only in crisis conditions. Operational definitions were provided for clarity, such as defining a safe work environment as cooperative efforts to prevent workplace injuries, and a stable work environment as job security with consistent, fair management practices.

Ten variables were identified from the literature: one monetary (salary) and nine non-monetary (safe work environment, stable work environment, career advancement opportunities, ongoing education/training, flexible work schedule for work–life balance, flexible schedule for secondary employment, technology/resources availability, family ties, and workplace socialization). Descriptive analysis was conducted for each variable, and for inferential testing, the nine non-monetary measures were aggregated into a composite variable for comparison with the monetary measure. The survey was sent to all 350 nurses in the hospital, and 54 complete responses were received, with 41 in Arabic and 13 in English. Responses were merged as both versions used identical numerical rating formats. The survey was distributed via Google Forms in both languages through the hospital's HR email directory, and the

English version was professionally translated into Arabic. All responses were complete, with no missing values.

The instrument achieved a Cronbach's alpha of 0.965, indicating excellent internal consistency and reliability. Data collection occurred between 1 October 2023 and 31 December 2023, with periodic email reminders sent to encourage participation. Collection ceased after 30 consecutive days without new responses, enabling analysis to begin. Data exported from Excel were analyzed using SPSS, applying both descriptive and inferential statistics. Means, standard deviations, and percentage distributions were calculated for each variable. Paired-samples t-tests assessed differences between conditions—normal vs. crisis, and with vs. without salary—and statistical significance was evaluated using p-values. The study tested four hypotheses: whether there are differences in the value of retention measures between normal and crisis situations; whether non-monetary measures without salary differ between normal and crisis situations; whether non-monetary measures in crisis differ with and without salary; and whether salary alone differs in value between normal and crisis situations. Each null and alternative hypothesis was explicitly stated to guide the analysis.

4. RESULTS

The demographic analysis was based on seven questions examining length of nursing experience, length of employment in the current institution, gender, age, marital status, parenthood, and proximity to the hospital. These variables were selected to evaluate professional experience, loyalty, socio-demographic influences, and the impact of commuting—particularly relevant in Lebanon, where poor public transportation and heavy Beirut traffic can negatively affect job satisfaction. Most nurses surveyed had more than three years of total experience, a positive indicator for institutional knowledge and patient care quality. However, the low proportion of nurses with less than two years' tenure may reflect recruitment challenges, possibly due to less competitive packages compared to foreign offers or limited hiring linked to stagnant institutional growth (see Figure 1). This trend is concerning given that healthcare expenditure in Lebanon rose from 7% of GDP in 2012 to 10.06% in 2021, suggesting growing service demand without proportional workforce expansion—heightening risks of overwork, burnout, and attrition.

Figure 1. *How long have you been working as a nurse?*

Retention appears strong, with 70.4% of respondents having remained with the same employer for at least three years, indicating either stable employment or limited mobility within a stagnant sector. Gender distribution showed 74.1% female and 25.9% male nurses, a notably high male representation compared with global averages (USA: 12.1% male; Europe: 16%). While this enhances workforce diversity, it also underscores the importance of competitive remuneration, particularly as men often serve as primary earners in Middle Eastern societies. Age distribution leaned toward a younger workforce, with 46.3% under 35, 35.2% aged 35–50, and 18.5% over 50 (see Figure ...).

Figure 2. Age distribution of nurses

While youth supports workload capacity, it may also mean less experience and weaker long-term loyalty, while the shrinking older cohort risks loss of mentorship and institutional culture. Marital status data indicated 51.9% single and 42.6% married, with parenthood evenly split (53.7% without children), potentially contributing to greater scheduling flexibility (see Figure ...).

Figure 3. Marital Status of Nurses

In terms of proximity, 57.4% lived within a 20-minute commute, benefiting work–life balance, while 42.6% faced longer commutes, which could elevate stress and dissatisfaction (see Figure ...). Addressing commuting challenges at institutional and governmental levels could strengthen both recruitment and retention.

Figure 4. Proximity to work

When examining the results of monetary and non-monetary measures in both normal and crisis situations, salary emerged as a consistently significant factor, increasing from 37.0% rating it “highly significant” in normal conditions to 50.0% during crisis, reflecting its heightened importance under financial strain (see Tables 1 and 2).

From Tables 1 and 2, one can also conclude the following:

- Workplace safety ranked nearly equal to salary, with 62.9% considering it significant or highly significant in normal times and 68.5% in crisis—likely influenced by heightened awareness from COVID-19, political unrest, and incidents like the Beirut Port.
- A stable work environment, defined by job security and consistent management, was valued similarly to salary under normal conditions (61.1%) and gained even greater importance in crisis (35.2% “highly significant” vs. 29.6% normal).
- Career advancement was moderately valued in normal times (31.5%) but dropped to just 13% “highly significant” in crisis, indicating that promotions lose appeal when financial and security concerns dominate.
- Ongoing education and training were strongly valued in normal conditions (66.6% significant/highly significant) but fell to 46.3% in crisis, showing that professional growth becomes secondary during hardship.
- Flexible scheduling for work–life balance remained consistently important (64.8% normal; 59.3% crisis), while flexibility for secondary employment became more important during crisis (29.6% “highly significant” vs. 11.1% normal).
- Availability of technology and tools remained stable in importance (64.8% significant/highly significant in both contexts), reflecting its role in both care quality and staff satisfaction.

- Family ties were rated significant by 55.6% in normal and 46.3% in crisis, suggesting that while culturally important, they may be outweighed by economic necessity.
- Socialization at work remained moderately significant (31.5% normal; 38.9% crisis) but ranked below financial and security-related factors.

Overall, salary, safety, and stability dominated retention priorities across all conditions, with education and technology valued but less so in crises, and flexibility—especially for secondary jobs—emerging as a practical, low-cost retention measure in hardship.

Table 1. Survey results concerning the value of monetary and non-monetary measures in normal situation

	Not Significant		Slightly Significant		Moderately Significant		Significant		Highly Significant	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
The Salary?	7	13.0%	6	11.1%	9	16.7%	12	22.2%	20	37.0%
A safe workplace?	4	7.4%	3	5.6%	13	24.1%	14	25.9%	20	37.0%
A stable work environment?	3	5.6%	6	11.1%	12	22.2%	17	31.5%	16	29.6%
The opportunity for career advancement and promotion?	5	9.3%	8	14.8%	17	31.5%	9	16.7%	15	27.8%
The on-going education and training with dedicated courses and programs?	2	3.7%	2	3.7%	14	25.9%	18	33.3%	18	33.3%
A flexible work schedule that permits work-life balance?	6	11.1%	4	7.4%	9	16.7%	16	29.6%	19	35.2%
A flexible work schedule that allows you to hold another job?	9	16.7%	10	18.5%	10	18.5%	19	35.2%	6	11.1%
The availability of technology and tools for modern healthcare delivery	2	3.7%	2	3.7%	15	27.8%	20	37.0%	15	27.8%
Family ties?	5	9.3%	3	5.6%	16	29.6%	13	24.1%	17	31.5%
Socialization at work?	5	9.3%	6	11.1%	17	31.5%	13	24.1%	13	24.1%

Table 2. Survey results for monetary and non-monetary measures in economic crisis situation

	Not Significant		Slightly Significant		Moderately Significant		Significant		Highly Significant	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Salary	7	13.0%	5	9.3%	9	16.7%	6	11.1%	27	50.0%
A safe workplace?	3	5.6%	3	5.6%	11	20.4%	16	29.6%	21	38.9%
A stable work environment?	5	9.3%	3	5.6%	17	31.5%	10	18.5%	19	35.2%
The opportunity for career advancement and promotion?	7	13.0%	7	13.0%	20	37.0%	13	24.1%	7	13.0%
The on-going education and training with dedicated courses and programs?	1	1.9%	6	11.1%	22	40.7%	14	25.9%	11	20.4%
A flexible work schedule that permits work-life balance?	3	5.6%	5	9.3%	14	25.9%	17	31.5%	15	27.8%
The availability of technology and tools for modern healthcare delivery	3	5.6%	6	11.1%	18	33.3%	15	27.8%	12	22.2%
Family ties?	6	11.1%	4	7.4%	19	35.2%	9	16.7%	16	29.6%
Socialization at work?	6	11.1%	6	11.1%	21	38.9%	10	18.5%	11	20.4%

When salary increases were excluded from consideration, safety and stability retained their position as top priorities in both normal and crisis conditions. In fact, during crisis, the proportion rating safety as “highly significant” rose from 29.6% to 40.7%, and for stability from 24.1% to 42.6%, underscoring their role when pay incentives are unavailable (see Table 3 and 4). Career advancement and training shifted toward moderate significance without salary, with sharper declines during crisis. Flexible scheduling and access to technology similarly dropped to moderate significance, although technology maintained steady importance for operational and cultural reasons. Family ties remained stable as a driver, reflecting deep-rooted cultural values, while socialization also shifted toward moderate significance, particularly in crisis, suggesting it should be supported but not prioritized over higher-impact measures. The results indicate that in the absence of financial incentives, ensuring job safety and stability offers the strongest retention impact, especially during crises.

Table 3. Survey results for non-monetary measures in normal situation, if salary is not an option

	Not Significant		Slightly Significant		Moderately Significant		Significant		Highly Significant	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Salary	1	1.9%	3	5.6%	16	29.6%	18	33.3%	16	29.6%
A safe workplace?	4	7.4%	2	3.7%	15	27.8%	20	37.0%	13	24.1%
A stable work environment?	6	11.1%	5	9.3%	20	37.0%	11	20.4%	12	22.2%
The opportunity for career advancement and promotion?	1	1.9%	2	3.7%	18	33.3%	19	35.2%	14	25.9%
The on-going education and training with dedicated courses and programs?	2	3.7%	3	5.6%	20	37%	15	27.8%	14	25.9%
A flexible work schedule that permits work-life balance?	7	13.0%	7	13.0%	16	29.6%	16	29.6%	8	14.8%
The availability of technology and tools for modern healthcare delivery	2	3.7%	2	3.7%	21	38.9%	16	29.6%	13	24.1%
Family ties?	4	7.4%	4	7.4%	17	31.5%	12	22.2%	17	31.5%
Socialization at work?	5	9.3%	6	11.1%	18	33.3%	10	18.5%	15	27.8%

Table 4. Survey results concerning the value of non-monetary measures in economic crisis situation, if salary is not an option

	Not Significant		Slightly Significant		Moderately Significant		Significant		Highly Significant	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Salary	3	5.6%	4	7.4%	13	24.1%	12	22.2%	22	40.7%
A safe workplace?	4	7.4%	3	5.6%	13	24.1%	11	20.4%	23	42.6%
A stable work environment?	4	7.4%	6	11.1%	23	42.6%	11	20.4%	10	18.5%
The opportunity for career advancement and promotion?	3	5.6%	3	5.6%	24	44.4%	14	25.9%	10	18.5%
The on-going education and training with dedicated courses and programs?	2	3.7%	3	5.6%	17	31.5%	14	25.9%	18	33.3%
A flexible work schedule that permits work-life balance?	7	13.0%	2	3.7%	18	33.3%	9	16.7%	18	33.3%
The availability of technology and tools for modern healthcare delivery	4	7.4%	1	1.9%	19	35.2%	17	31.5%	13	24.1%
Family ties?	5	9.3%	2	3.7%	18	33.3%	12	22.2%	17	31.5%
Socialization at work?	9	16.7%	5	9.3%	21	38.9%	10	18.5%	9	16.7%

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that, while monetary compensation is a primary driver of nurse retention, non-monetary factors such as workplace safety and stability are almost equally influential, especially during crises. This insight aligns with global research indicating that, in both high- and low-resource settings, nurses evaluate the totality of their work environment when making career decisions. Economic insecurity, political instability, and public health emergencies amplify the perceived value of safety and job security, suggesting that interventions focused solely on salary may be insufficient to retain skilled personnel in any context.

The universality of these findings is supported by studies from multiple regions experiencing workforce shortages. In sub-Saharan Africa, South-East Asia, and parts of Eastern Europe, nurses consistently prioritize safety, manageable workloads, and organizational stability alongside remuneration. Lebanon's unique economic crisis accentuates these priorities, but the broader principle—that professional satisfaction depends on a combination of material and psychosocial factors—applies to healthcare systems worldwide, particularly in environments subject to political turbulence or economic volatility.

Our data reveal that during crisis conditions, the perceived importance of career advancement and educational opportunities diminishes relative to immediate safety and income needs. This trend resonates with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, which posits that individuals prioritize basic physiological and security needs over higher-order motivations when resources are constrained. Globally, this phenomenon suggests that retention strategies must be adaptive: while professional development may attract and motivate staff under normal circumstances, it cannot replace foundational safety and financial security during systemic shocks.

Flexible scheduling emerges as another universally relevant retention factor. In Lebanon, the ability to engage in secondary employment or adjust shifts for work–life balance was rated highly during economic hardship, reflecting a coping strategy to offset financial insufficiency. Across countries facing staffing shortages or unstable economies, flexible scheduling offers a cost-effective, scalable intervention that simultaneously addresses personal needs and mitigates turnover. This underscores the potential for non-monetary incentives to supplement, rather than substitute, salary interventions in diverse healthcare contexts.

The consistency in the perceived value of technology and resource availability indicates that nurses universally appreciate environments that facilitate high-quality care. Access to modern tools enhances workflow efficiency, reduces fatigue, and signals institutional investment in both staff and patients. Whether in Lebanon, Europe, or North America, technology-rich workplaces contribute to professional satisfaction, highlighting that investments in infrastructure and operational support are globally relevant levers for workforce retention.

Family ties and workplace socialization were moderately significant in both normal and crisis conditions, reflecting cultural and relational dimensions that influence retention. While these factors may vary in intensity across cultures, they point to the universal role of social and emotional support in professional sustainability. Globally, health systems can strengthen retention by fostering collegiality, mentorship, and organizational cultures that recognize employees as whole individuals rather than solely as service providers.

The study also illustrates the interplay between salary and non-monetary incentives. In the absence of competitive compensation, safety and stability assume an even greater relative importance. This finding suggests a broader application: health systems worldwide can design context-specific packages that leverage low-cost, high-impact non-monetary measures to enhance retention when financial resources are constrained. Thus, holistic approaches, rather than singular focus on remuneration, are universally advantageous.

The emigration patterns observed in Lebanon echo global trends where economic downturns, political instability, and workforce dissatisfaction drive skilled nurses to seek opportunities abroad. This reinforces the principle that health system resilience depends not only on local incentives but also on macro-level stability. Universal lessons can be drawn: safeguarding nurses' well-being and security, ensuring predictable working conditions, and creating supportive policies are critical for retention in any healthcare system vulnerable to labor migration.

Integrating these findings into policy frameworks highlights the importance of multi-tiered strategies. Hospital-level interventions, such as occupational safety measures, flexible scheduling, and professional development programs, must be complemented by national-level actions addressing security, labor rights, and economic stability. This combined approach is relevant not only to Lebanon but also to countries facing similar systemic pressures, indicating that retention is as much a societal concern as an institutional one.

Finally, the study emphasizes that retention strategies should be dynamic, responsive, and evidence-based. By recognizing the shifting priorities of nurses under varying socio-economic conditions, health administrators worldwide can tailor interventions to maximize effectiveness. Whether in resource-constrained countries or wealthier nations experiencing workforce pressures, the principle remains: sustainable retention depends on the integration of monetary, non-monetary, and systemic measures, with attention to both individual needs and broader contextual challenges.

A visual summary table translating the Lebanese findings into globally relevant nurse retention strategies is shown in the following table.

Retention Factor	Lebanese Findings	Universal Relevance / Global Implications	Recommended Strategy
Salary / Compensation	Most highly valued, especially during crisis; increased from 37% “highly significant” to 50%	Globally, compensation remains the primary driver of retention; competitive pay prevents migration	Benchmark salaries regionally; adjust for inflation and cost of living; consider hazard pay during crises
Workplace Safety	Nearly equal to salary; 68.5% rated “significant/highly significant” during crisis	Safety is universally critical; affects job satisfaction, reduces burnout and turnover	Implement robust infection control, safe staffing ratios, violence prevention, and secure transportation
Stable Work Environment	Highly valued in crisis; 42.6% rated “highly significant” without salary	Job security and consistent management practices are universally appreciated; critical in unstable regions	Establish transparent HR policies, contract security, and predictable managerial practices
Career Advancement / Promotion	Moderately valued in crisis; declined from 31.5% to 13% “highly significant”	Universal trend: advancement motivates retention under stable conditions but loses appeal during hardship	Provide clear promotion pathways, mentorship, and structured career ladders; prioritize during stable periods
Ongoing Education / Training	Highly valued normally; reduced importance during crisis	Globally, professional development enhances satisfaction and skill retention	Offer continuing education, e-learning, and certification programs; integrate into institutional culture
Flexible Scheduling (Work-Life Balance)	Consistently important; 64.8% normal, 59.3% crisis	Flexible scheduling universally reduces burnout and improves retention	Implement shift flexibility, part-time options, and remote work where feasible
Flexible Scheduling (Secondary Job)	Increased importance in crisis; 11.1% → 29.6% “highly significant”	Flexibility to supplement income is relevant in economically stressed regions	Allow policies for secondary employment or shift swaps; monitor workload balance
Technology / Tools Availability	Steady importance; ~64% rated significant	Modern tools improve workflow, efficiency, and satisfaction worldwide	Invest in electronic health records, monitoring devices, and digital support tools
Family Ties	Moderately important; reduced from 55.6% → 46.3%	Cultural variation exists, but work-life integration is universally recognized	Encourage family-friendly policies, childcare support, and flexible leave
Workplace Socialization	Moderate significance; ~31.5%–38.9%	Collegial environment improves retention and mental health globally	Promote team-building, peer support, mentorship, and positive workplace culture

6. CONCLUSION

Lebanon is currently facing a dual and compounding loss in its nursing workforce: the emigration of experienced nurses and the departure of newly graduated, highly educated professionals. The loss of senior nurses erodes the mentorship capacity essential for transferring tacit knowledge, clinical expertise, and institutional culture to the next generation. Simultaneously, the outflow of new graduates—who represent the future of the profession—weakens the system's ability to meet rising healthcare demands driven by population growth, epidemiological transition, and increasing patient complexity. Together, these trends undermine both the quality of nursing education and the delivery of patient care, with well-documented downstream effects on patient safety, satisfaction, and clinical outcomes.

This study confirms that salary remains a central determinant of job satisfaction and retention, particularly in the context of Lebanon's prolonged economic crisis, where hyperinflation and currency devaluation have severely diminished purchasing power. However, findings also underscore that a safe and stable work environment is valued almost equally to salary. Here, "safety" extends far beyond clinical occupational hazards to encompass the broader socio-political landscape. Catastrophic events such as the 2020 Beirut Port Explosion, coupled with persistent political instability, economic collapse, and intermittent civil unrest, have generated a pervasive sense of insecurity. This chronic instability not only shapes nurses' perceptions of their workplace but also influences their broader life decisions, including whether to remain in the country.

The findings raise an important policy question: should ensuring safety and stability be considered solely the responsibility of healthcare employers, or should it also be recognized as a fundamental obligation of the state? Framed through Maslow's hierarchy of needs, the results reflect a shift toward prioritizing basic physiological and safety needs during crises, with both safety and stability ranking at levels comparable to salary. Similarly, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory offers explanatory insight: while motivators such as career advancement, recognition, and professional growth remain important, their impact diminishes during times of acute socio-economic stress. In such contexts, hygiene factors—particularly salary and workplace safety—become paramount, with their absence creating job dissatisfaction that no amount of motivational effort can offset. These findings suggest that during crises, retention strategies should focus first on strengthening hygiene factors to prevent dissatisfaction, and only once these are secure should attention turn to enhancing motivators that drive long-term engagement.

Another notable finding is that under stable, non-crisis conditions, ongoing education, training, and professional development can hold value equal to salary in influencing job satisfaction. Moreover, both nurses and patients place significant importance on access to advanced healthcare technologies. This points to an administrative strategy that invests not only in human capital but also in modern medical tools and infrastructure. Such investments appear to have a dual effect: improving clinical outcomes and fostering a sense of professional pride and satisfaction among nursing staff, while also reinforcing a culture of quality within healthcare institutions.

The sustainability of Lebanon's healthcare sector depends on its ability to both recruit and retain skilled nurses. While financial incentives remain the most potent retention driver, many employers cannot match the salary packages offered by international recruiters, particularly given the constraints imposed by third-party payers, capped reimbursement rates, and limited institutional budgets. This study therefore sought to identify non-monetary strategies capable of offsetting these limitations. Although inferential statistical analysis did not produce statistically significant differences, descriptive results suggest that workplace safety and stability hold substantial perceived value for nurses and could serve as critical levers in slowing migration. Importantly, achieving such conditions will require more than hospital-level interventions; it will demand coordinated national action involving the Lebanese government, the

Ministry of Public Health, and professional nursing bodies to address both occupational safety standards and broader societal security.

The study's primary limitation lies in its relatively small sample size ($n = 54$), which may limit the generalizability of its findings across Lebanon's diverse healthcare settings. Additionally, there is a potential for recall bias, as participants were asked to reflect on pre-crisis conditions while completing the survey during the crisis period. However, given the rapid onset and severity of the crisis, coupled with the proximity of pre-crisis conditions to the time of data collection, such bias is likely minimal. Future research with larger, more representative samples and longitudinal designs could further validate these findings and help refine retention strategies for the Lebanese nursing workforce in both stable and crisis contexts.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Efforts to recruit and retain nurses in Lebanon must continue to prioritize salary improvements to the greatest extent financially feasible, as compensation remains the single most influential factor shaping nurses' career decisions—particularly in periods of acute economic crisis. In the current context of currency devaluation, hyperinflation, and international competition for skilled healthcare professionals, salary enhancements are not merely a financial matter but a core retention strategy. Nevertheless, when substantial salary increases are not viable due to budgetary constraints, third-party payer limitations, or institutional funding shortfalls, alternative strategies must be deployed to maintain workforce stability. Chief among these are the reinforcement of workplace safety and the assurance of a stable employment environment.

In this study, a safe work environment is defined as one in which employers and employees collaborate to prevent occupational injuries, mitigate workplace hazards, and promote a culture of health and security. A stable work environment refers to conditions characterized by secure employment contracts, consistent and transparent management practices, and equitable treatment of staff. While hospital administrations can directly influence several components of these conditions—such as safety protocols, managerial consistency, and internal conflict resolution—the broader dimension of stability requires active governmental engagement. Legislative and regulatory frameworks are essential to guarantee job security, uphold equitable management practices, and ensure the consistent enforcement of labor protections across all regions. This is particularly critical in peripheral and underserved areas, where strengthening stability could help redress geographic imbalances in nurse distribution and service coverage.

Hospital administrations can enhance workplace safety through measures that minimize exposure to occupational hazards, such as infection control protocols, safe staffing ratios, and the provision of adequate protective equipment—efforts that proved vital during the COVID-19 pandemic. Professional unions and medical associations have played a pivotal role in advocating for these measures and supporting their implementation. However, without sustained government oversight, such initiatives risk being inconsistently applied or under-resourced. Moreover, the concept of workplace safety should extend beyond clinical hazards to include protection from workplace violence, safe and reliable transportation for staff, and measures to mitigate risks linked to the broader socio-political environment. In Lebanon's case, the persistent threat of armed conflict, civil unrest, and political instability remains a significant driver of nurse emigration, creating a safety challenge that far exceeds the capacity of individual hospitals to resolve.

Given these realities, it is imperative that employers, unions, and professional bodies form a unified coalition to advocate for stronger governmental intervention in matters of safety and stability. This advocacy should push for national-level initiatives that address both occupational protections and the macro-level drivers of insecurity. Such measures might include enforcing labor rights legislation, strengthening healthcare infrastructure resilience, improving national security, and ensuring equitable regional distribution of healthcare resources. Without these broader structural safeguards, hospital-level efforts alone will be insufficient to stem the ongoing loss of nursing talent. Ultimately, retaining Lebanon's nursing workforce will require a coordinated approach in which salary competitiveness, workplace safety, and national stability are treated as interconnected pillars of a sustainable healthcare system.

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